

Research Article

Utilization of Okra Stem Waste Extracts for the Development of Dual Network and Self-Healing Polysaccharide/Gelatin Hydrogels With Natural Crosslinker Succinic Acid

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In this study, okra gum polysaccharides derived from okra stem waste extract were utilized as a raw material for synthesizing hydrogel matrices. The polysaccharide-rich okra gum was combined with gelatin to enhance the gelation properties of the resulting hydrogels. To assess and compare the self-healing capabilities of the fabricated hydrogels, a natural and nontoxic crosslinking agent, succinic acid, was introduced into the hydrogel formulations at different ratios (5%, 7.5%, and 10% *w/v*), imparting a dual network structure to the hydrogel matrices. Characterization of the synthesized hydrogels was conducted using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses, providing a comprehensive understanding of their structural and thermal properties. Furthermore, a series of three self-healing assays, including gel block fusion tests, electrical conductivity assessments, and mechanical evaluations, were employed to evaluate the influence of succinic acid on the self-healing efficacy of the okra–gelatin hydrogel composites. These investigations revealed promising outcomes, with the succinic acid–enhanced hydrogel formulation exhibiting a remarkable self-healing ratio of 95% and an electrical conductivity recovery rate of 96.2%. Additionally, incorporating succinic acid in different proportions into the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel resulted in decreased swelling values. These findings underscore the significant potential of succinic acid as a crosslinking agent in enhancing the self-healing properties of polysaccharide-based hydrogel matrices, thereby paving the way for their promising applications in various fields, such as sustainable hydrogel sensors. These materials can provide environmentally friendly options for monitoring physiological and environmental changes, while their enhanced self-healing properties contribute to more durable and reliable sensors for various electronic applications.

Keywords: natural hydrogel; okra gum; self-healing; succinic acid; waste management

1. Introduction

Agricultural waste represents a valuable resource for producing sustainable and value-added products through recycling and conversion processes. Various agricultural by-products such as rice husk [1], sugarcane bagasse [2], and crop residues [3] have been successfully recycled to produce a wide

range of products. These products include biofuels, biogas, bio-oil, biofertilizers, cultivation materials, adsorbents, enzymes by fermentation, and high-value chemicals [4–8]. In addition, one of the value-added products examined in waste utilization is natural hydrogels.

Natural hydrogels are known for their extraordinary self-healing properties. This feature allows them to repair

damage and restore structural integrity autonomously [9]. Several studies have explored different mechanisms to achieve self-healing in natural hydrogels, such as host–guest interactions [10], metal–ion coordination [11], hydrophobic interactions [12], hydrogen bonding [13], and dynamic covalent bonds, to enable self-healing [14]. In polysaccharide–protein polymer combinations, the self-healing effect is provided by weak hydrogen bonds. Green crosslinkers offer a versatile solution when combined with biomacromolecules or polymers, catering to various needs such as adhesion, flexibility, and adjustability in physical or chemical properties [15]. Natural options like tannic acid, citric acid, gallic acid, and succinic acid (SA) are widely used in hydrogel studies [16]. SA, derived from amber fermentation, finds applications across agricultural, food, and pharmaceutical sectors [17]. It positively impacts human metabolism and poses no risk of accumulation in the body. With its two carboxyl groups, SA can serve as a crosslinking agent [18]. In the dissolution process of gelatin (GEL) and carboxylic acid in water, the carboxyl groups of dicarboxylic acids are expected to ionically interact with the positively charged amino groups on GEL polymers. This interaction reduces the amount of free amino groups available. Furthermore, dicarboxylic acids used for polymer dissolution can provide protons to facilitate the dissolution process. They also serve as ionic crosslinking reagents, fostering ionic interactions between the amino groups of the polymer and the two carboxylic groups of the acid molecules. These interactions contribute to the overall solubility and structural stability of the resulting polymer solution or hydrogel [19].

Natural gums, which possess self-healing properties and sustainability, are abundant polysaccharides that contain β (1–4) bonds. They are one of the most promising materials for the production of hydrogels. The large amount of OH groups on the surface of natural gums, which are cellulose-based polysaccharides, allows the formation of cellulose chains with excellent mechanical properties, serving as a mechanical strengthener. Furthermore, large hydroxyl groups on cellulose enable self-healing via reversible hydrogen bonds [20, 21]. Okra gum was used as a polysaccharide-based polymer in this study. Okra, scientifically named *Abelmoschus esculentus*, is a commonly consumed nutritious plant [22]. Okra gum stands out from typical biological polysaccharides due to its high fructose content, which contributes to its strong adhesive properties [23]. The constituting monosaccharides of okra gum include D-galactose, L-rhamnose, mannose, D-galacturonic acid, glucose, and arabinose [24, 25].

By combining the natural polymers to obtain hydrogel, it is possible to develop and improve the inherently disadvantageous properties of these polymers. Amelia et al. produced higher-strength and more durable hydrogels by combining the brittle, low-strength, and easily water-soluble structure of the GEL polymer with the polysaccharide-based polymer obtained from the waste of avocado seeds [26]. In addition, hydrogels produced with dual polymer combinations have increased failure stress, toughness, self-healing properties, and elasticity due to the dual network mechanism compared to single-network polymer hydrogel [27]. Since the bonds

between hydrogel polymer networks depend on “reversible chain association–dissociation” mechanisms, it does not create adverse effects such as the breaking of covalent bonds in chemically crosslinked hydrogels [28].

In this study, after the fibers extracted from the stem structure were taken from the digestion bath, the gum remaining in the bath was used for hydrogel production. Dual network, self-healing hydrogels were obtained by treating polysaccharide-based okra gum and GEL polymers with SA, a natural crosslinker. In the literature, there are methods for obtaining okra hydrogels, as shown in Table 1. However, okra gums are generally obtained from okra pods. The zero-waste approach is first discussed in this study. Okra gum efficiency was calculated from fiber extraction, and the effects of SA on the self-healing properties of hydrogel samples were examined. GEL was selected over other polymers due to its natural abundance, biocompatibility, and biodegradability, making it an accessible and sustainable choice for hydrogel formation [35]. Unlike synthetic polymers such as polyacrylamide (PAAm) or polyethylene glycol (PEG), which lack inherent biological recognition sites and often require chemical modifications (e.g., functionalization with bioactive molecules) to improve biocompatibility, GEL naturally possesses functional groups ($-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{OH}$) that enable effective crosslinking with okra gum and SA, enhancing both mechanical strength and conductivity [36]. This study is expected to add an innovative perspective to waste evaluation approaches. It is aimed at setting an example for using sustainable raw material resources to produce eco-friendly, value-added products by improving the mechanical properties of natural hydrogels with biocompatible and nontoxic chemicals. These enhanced hydrogels can be employed in various electronic applications, including textile-based wearable sensors, providing both sustainable and innovative solutions [37–39].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials. Okra was harvested in the Empoli region of Florence starting in November, and the plant stems were left in the field. The collected stem waste was then gathered, amounting to a total of 3 kg.

SA (MW: 118.09 g/mol; boiling point: 235°C; melting point: 182°C; density: 1.56 g/cm³), acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$, formula: CH_3COCH_3 ; MW: 58.08 g/mol; boiling point: 56.2°C; melting point: -95.4°C ; density: 0.792 g/cm³), and GEL Type A (100 g GEL from porcine skin, powder, gel strength ~ 300 g bloom, Type A, dry powder) were procured from Sigma-Aldrich Italy. Distilled water was used as a solvent for all hydrogel solutions. All chemicals were used without any further purification.

2.2. Okra Gum Extraction. Okra stem waste was soaked in closed containers in a water bath for 20 days; after which the fibers were separated from the stem waste. According to the literature, gum extraction from okra plants typically involves grinding the seeds or boiling the sliced plants [40, 41]. However, this study is aimed at contributing to the literature by separating the gum from the okra’s outer layer and

TABLE 1: Overview of okra gum hydrogel studies in the literature.

Polymers	Crosslinking agent	Chemical interactions	Self-healing	End usage	Reference
Okra gum + polyvinyl alcohol–guar gum	Citric acid	Hydrogen bonds	No	Drug delivery	[29]
Okra gum + polyvinyl alcohol	Borax	Boronic ester bonds + hydrogen bonds	Yes	Strain sensor	[30]
Sodium alginate + okra gel	—	Hydrogen bonds + electrostatic interactions	No	Biomedical applications	[31]
Okra gum + acrylic acid monomers	Ethylene glycol dimethacrylate	Hydrogen bonds	No	Drug delivery	[32]
Okra gum + gelatin + methacrylic acid monomers	Methylene bisacrylamide	Electrostatic interactions	No	Drug delivery	[33]
Okra gum + chia seeds	Acrylic acid and acrylamide monomers	Hydrogen bonds	No	Drug delivery	[34]

stem fibers within the stem waste for the first time. As shown in Figure 1a, the gum precipitates during the fiber extraction process. The okra fiber, visible in Figure 1b, was separated after extraction. The precipitated gum was then filtered using muslin cloth and further filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper (125 mm) for 24 h. To purify the gum, 20% *v/v* acetone was added to the okra gum obtained from the stem waste, and the mixture was filtered again.

The mixture was subjected to ultrasonic treatment (12.75-mm diameter, 60 kHz, model 750 W, Vibra-Cell, United States) at 40°C for 10 min. After ultrasonication, the okra gum was centrifuged for 10 min and vacuum-filtered. The filtered mucilage was extracted several times with 96% ethanol solution at room temperature to remove chlorophyll. The effect of chlorophyll on the powdered gum can be seen in Figure 1c,d [42]. A portion of the filtered gum was dried overnight at 45°C in a convection oven. This process was repeated five times; after which the dried samples were pulverized into powder using a dual-blade ceramic ball mill (28,000 rpm, Huangcheng, China). Two grinding techniques were employed to achieve particle sizes between 250 and 1400 μm : gentle grinding (approximately 1 min) and intense grinding (approximately 5 min), with the latter producing particles as fine as 150–200 μm suitable for hydrogel preparation [43]. The okra gum, ground to a fine powder with particle sizes of 150–200 μm , was then stored in airtight containers for hydrogel production.

2.3. Fabrication of Hydrogels. Various samples were prepared by mixing okra gum powder obtained from okra stem waste and GEL polymer. Reference hydrogel samples of OK-GUM (10% *w/v* okra powder) and GEL (5% *w/v* GEL) were also prepared by dissolving them in 100-mL distilled water. The mixtures were stirred continuously at 1400 rpm for 40 min at room temperature to achieve maximum hydration and prevent clumping. Subsequently, the temperature was raised to 70°C and stirred for 20 min. All prepared solutions were poured into 2 × 2 × 2 cm silicone molds, cooled to room temperature, and stored at 3°C–4°C. OK-GUM-GEL and OK-GUM-GELSA samples were prepared using the solvent casting method as shown in Figure 2.

Firstly, 10% *w/v* okra powder and 5% *w/v* GEL polymers were dissolved in 100-mL distilled water at 50°C–70°C for 2 h, followed by pouring the mixture into a glass petri dish and allowing it to dry at 50°C for up to 12 h to produce OK-GUM-GEL hydrogels. For the production of OK-GUM-GELSA, SA at 5%, 7.5%, and 10% *w/v* concentrations was added dropwise to a binary polymer solution, and the reaction was completed at pH 5.2. The hydrogel mixtures were allowed to rest at 37°C for 1 h to complete physical and chemical crosslinking and gelling. All solutions were poured into 2 × 2 × 2 cm silicone molds, cooled to room temperature, and stored overnight at 3°C–4°C in a refrigerator for complete gelation. Each measurement was performed in triplicate at specified intervals [30, 44].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Okra Gum Efficiency Calculation. The percentage yields of the obtained okra gum powder, unprocessed okra stems (gram) (m_0) and extracted okra gum powder (gram) (m_1), were calculated using Equation (1) [45]:

$$\text{Yield of okra gum powder} = \frac{m_1}{m_0}. \quad (1)$$

In the study, the yield of okra gum obtained after collecting and extracting the remaining gums left in the bath during fiber extraction from okra stem waste is 27%. Literature reports indicate varied percentages for okra gum. For example, Bhat and Tharanathan reported approximately 1% [46], Kaur et al. achieved around 0.5% [45], and Archana et al. claimed 8.6% [47]. These differences may be attributed to factors such as the cultivation region, okra pod type and part used (crown, pulp), maturation stage (fresh/mature okra), and physical state of okra (dried powder, hydrated pod). Several researchers have explored optimal extraction conditions, including varying extraction times, temperatures, cycles, and solvent-to-material ratios. Lee et al. achieved a 2.38% yield using a water extraction method under conditions of 70°C, 2 h, 2.5 *w/w* solvent loading, and agitation at 200 rpm [48]. Samavati also used water as a solvent, resulting in a high 17% yield, differing in extraction

FIGURE 1: (a) Extraction of gum from okra stem waste through degradation. (b) Obtained okra fibers. (c) Powdered forms of gum from okra stem waste containing chlorophyll. (d) Okra gum powder from which chlorophyll has been removed.

FIGURE 2: Fabrication steps for hydrogels based on okra stem waste gum.

numbers and water-to-material ratio [49]. The previously published procedures have never applied a zero-waste approach to okra gum and hydrogels which is first evaluated in this study. In comparison to the literature, the reason for achieving a high yield of okra gum is the presence of a significant amount of gum in okra stem waste compared to okra pods. Our extraction method achieves a 27% yield, higher than some conventional methods like direct boiling or seed grinding, which often result in material loss. The process is standardized and reproducible, involving water

immersion, multistep filtration, and acetone treatment to enhance purity. Using only water, acetone, and ethanol, it avoids complex chemical treatments, making it scalable and environmentally friendly by minimizing solvent use and reducing chemical waste. These advantages highlight the efficiency and sustainability of our approach.

3.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis. Hydrogel samples were frozen at -20°C for 24 h and subsequently freeze-dried at -85°C for 24 h (Christ-Alfa 2-4 Model,

FIGURE 3: SEM images showing surface morphologies of hydrogel samples: (a) OK-GUM, (b) OK-GUM-GEL, and (c) OK-GUM-GELSA.

Martin Christ GmbH). Cross sections were taken from the dried hydrogel samples and coated with a 200 Å gold layer. The morphologies of the dried hydrogel strips were examined using a JEOL JSM 6060 LV SEM.

SEM analysis of OK-GUM, OK-GUM-GEL, and OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel composites is given in Figure 3. Figure 3a shows the morphologies of hydrogels derived from okra stem waste (OK-GUM), depicting microstructures (small images ~ 1 and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in size). Upon examining the surface morphology of OK-GUM gel, it was observed that it possessed surface porosity and depth. The surface images are heterogeneous in the images of the OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel composite (Figure 3b), and a scaly and porous structure similar to that of the OK-GUM hydrogel is evident. The gum-incorporated hydrogel exhibits a typical surface morphology of a polymeric structure. The porous structure in the surface morphology of OK-GUM and OK-GUM-GEL hydrogels can be attributed to their high swelling behavior, contributing to their aqueous structure. It can be said that OK-GUM and OK-GUM-GEL hydrogels enhance liquid diffusion in the polymeric network and water retention capacity. In the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel composite, SA has been coated on the surface and has formed crosslinks (Figure 3c), indicating a decrease in swelling behavior. The reduction in porous structure in surface morphologies and the more homogeneous microstructure of the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel composite compared to the heterogeneous structure observed in OK-GUM and OK-GUM-GEL hydro-

gel composites can be attributed to SA's crosslinking properties [50–52].

3.3. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis.

The structures of powdered and hydrogel samples obtained from okra gum were characterized by FTIR analysis using a PerkinElmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer with attenuated total reflectance (ATR), scanning in the range of $450\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. FTIR spectra of SA, GEL, OK-GUM, OK-GUM-GEL, and OK-GUM-GELSA samples are shown in Figure 4a, and all the important frequencies are given in Figure 4b. All samples were evaluated at $600\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ wavenumber. In Figure 4a, the acyl group of SA acid falls at 1712 cm^{-1} [53]. The spectrum of SA also shows very large O-H stretching vibrations between 3300 and 2500 cm^{-1} superimposed to the stretching bands of C-H bonds. Overall, the spectrum confirms the presence of carboxylic groups forming hydrogen-bonded dimers.

When the absorption bands of GEL polymer were examined, in accordance with the literature, N-H stretching appeared at 3300 cm^{-1} , while CH_2 asymmetric stretching at 2926 cm^{-1} , C-N-H amide I vibration at 1631 cm^{-1} , bending vibrations of N-H groups at 1545 cm^{-1} (amide II band), and symmetric vibrations of the methyl group at 1447 cm^{-1} peaks were observed [54]. For okra mucilage spectra, characteristic bands at 1248 cm^{-1} are assigned to C-O stretching and 1035 cm^{-1} C-O-C stretching bands in polysaccharides. Also, the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group at 1578 cm^{-1} was observed [55]. After

	ν [cm ⁻¹]	Chemical groups
Succinic acid/succinate	888	Asymmetric stretching of C-C
	1547	Asymmetric stretching of COO
	1712	C=O stretching
	2856	CH ₂ stretching
	2926	CH ₃ stretching
	3300	O-H stretching
Gelatin	1161	C-H bending
	1240	Am ide III
	1447	NH ₂ bending
	1545	Am ide II
	1631	Am ide I
	2849	CH ₂ asymmetric stretching
	3300	N-H stretching
Okra gum	1035	C-O-C stretching
	1248	C-O stretching
	1320	C-H stretching
	1432	C-H stretching
	1578	C=N stretching
	3270	O-H stretching
OK-GUM-GEL	3300	O-H and N-H stretching
	2862	CH ₂ asymmetric stretching
OK-GUM-GELSA	888	Asymmetric stretching of C-C
	1312	Symmetric stretching of COO
	1552	Asymmetric stretching of COO
	1614	C=O stretching
	2934	CH ₂ stretching
	3295	O-H stretching

FIGURE 4: (a) FTIR spectra of succinic acid, gelatin, okra gum, OK-GUM-GEL, and OK-GUM-GELSA. (b) Key frequencies of hydrogel components and hydrogel samples.

hydrogel formation with GEL and okra mucilage (OK-GUM-GEL), the CH₂ asymmetric stretching at 2862 cm⁻¹ peak belonging to GEL decreased in intensity due to its interaction with okra mucilage. The width and intensity of the O-H bands between 3500 and 3000 cm⁻¹ increased due to the weak hydrogen bonds formed between the binary polymer reaction. Finally, after treatment with SA, the peak intensity of the OK-GUM-GELSA sample at 2856 and 2926 cm⁻¹ also increases due to the CH₂ groups in SA. Addi-

tionally, asymmetric C-C bonds that give the 888 cm⁻¹ peak in SA are visible in the OK-GUM-GELSA sample [56]. The intense new band falling at 1552 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the asymmetric stretching of carboxylate groups of SA.

Considering the pH measured on the solution used to prepare OK-GUM-GELSA (5.2), SA was added as a mixture of the corresponding monocarboxylate and dicarboxylate to the polymer mixture (pK₁ 4.2, pK₂ 5.6). The carboxylate units could have formed either hydrogen bonds with the

biopolymers or ionic complexes with cations present in the starting materials. Paris Junior et al. previously observed the strong asymmetric and weak symmetric absorption bands of potassium succinate at 1559 and 1392, respectively. In our spectra, carboxylate bands are observed at 1552 and 1312. Overall, these observations point to a possible establishment of an ionic crosslinking mechanism from the succinate. The salt formed crystallizes after gel drying. Carboxylate could interact with cations present in the gel, either inorganic or ammonium, pending functionalities of the GEL polymer.

3.4. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Analysis. DSC analysis was conducted to examine the exothermic and endothermic changes of the hydrogels during thermal treatment. DSC (PerkinElmer) samples, weighing 5 mg each, were placed in aluminum pans and subjected to a temperature range of 0°C–400°C with a heating rate of 10°C/min.

DSC diagrams were obtained for OK-GUM-GEL and OK-GUM-GELSA samples under nitrogen between 0°C and 350°C with a temperature ramp of 10°C/min. So far, the glass transition temperature for okra mucilage could not be detected [56, 57], as well as in this study for okra hydrogels. Maximum endothermic peaks were observed at 113.27°C for OK-GUM-GEL and at 131.34°C for OK-GUM-GELSA. The endothermic peak observed for OK-GUM-GEL occurs during the evaporation of water molecules in the hydrogel structure (Figure 5a). Since the energy required to break the ionic bond between water molecules and the polysaccharides contained in okra mucilage is higher, the water evaporation temperature in the structure is higher than the boiling temperature. Two different endothermic peaks are observed in the OK-GUM-GELSA sample (Figure 5b). While the first peak occurs due to the removal of water molecules in the hydrogel structure, the second peak shows the amount of energy required to remove the occluded water from SA crystals [58].

3.5. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis. The XRD spectra of the samples were scanned using a diffractometer (Empyrean, PANalytical, Netherlands) with Co-K α radiation. Diffractograms were taken between 5° and 40° (2θ) at a rate of 1°/min (2θ) and with a step size of 0.02° (2θ). Each measurement was carried out at least three times ($n \geq 3$), and the average values were used for analysis.

The XRD crystallization characterizations of OK-GUM, OK-GUM-GEL, and OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel samples are given in Figure 5c,d. The patterns of OK-GUM-containing hydrogels with the XRD method are amorphous [34, 59]. When the GEL XRD curve is examined, it shows no significant peak confirming the amorphous structure as much as OK-GUM. It was observed that the peak of OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel exhibited both amorphous nature and crystallinity by forming a broad peak broadening around $2\theta = 20^\circ$, corresponding to the triple helical configuration of GEL [60]. However, a small sharp peak is seen at $2\theta = 25^\circ$. It shows the minor crystalline nature of the sample in the OK-GUM synergy of GEL.

In addition to a large diffraction peak in the peak change, peaks formed with the addition of $2\theta = 27^\circ$ (7.5% SA), $2\theta = 32^\circ$, and the second peak with intensity (10% SA) are seen at $2\theta = 28^\circ$, $2\theta = 38^\circ$. With the increase in the amount of SA, the intense peak exhibits a broad and sharp peak between $2\theta = 30^\circ - 40^\circ$. SA has created an intense peak shift from $2\theta = 25^\circ$. This increase in the peak intensity can be explained as the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds between the amino and hydroxyl groups in the GEL chain of the SA structure and the COOH group of the ionic OK-GUM hydrogel and the increase in volume. While SA creates a regular crystalline order, it is interpreted as the presence of an amorphous structure together with the increase in water retention capacity, which increases the water retention capacity with OK-GUM and GEL. This model shows that the formation of density greater than 20° between the crosslinking agent SA and OK-GUM-GEL leads to regularity in the structure of intermolecular and intramolecular bonds [61].

3.6. Self-Healing Tests. Gel block fusion testing [62], electrical self-healing test [63], and mechanical testing [26] were performed to test the self-healing properties of the hydrogel. For the gel block fusion test, the hydrogel sample was divided into two parts with the help of a sharp razor blade. Then, the separated parts were painted in different colors, methylene blue and methyl orange, to help visualize self-healing. After the samples were combined manually, they were kept at 37°C for 1 h. Also, the electrical self-healing properties of the hydrogel test were performed by using the light bulb method. The light bulb before cutting the hydrogel and the light bulb after cutting and healing are visually presented. Additionally, the electrical resistivity of the samples was measured using a multimeter before cutting and after self-healing. The electrical recovery percentage was calculated. Finally, as a mechanical recovery evaluation, tensile strength and elongation of hydrogel samples were measured. Samples were cut into small strips of 10-mm width and 50-mm length; crosshead speed was 5 mm/min. INSTRON mechanical testing machine was used for mechanical tests.

The enhancement of self-healing properties in hydrogels by the addition of SA is attributed to the ionic interactions between natural polymers and SA. Two qualitative healing analyses were conducted to reveal the effect of SA on the self-healing properties of hydrogels, providing valuable information about the regenerative abilities of these advanced materials.

In the first analysis, the hydrogels were cut into two pieces using a razor blade. Each resulting piece was then stained with different colors—methyl blue and methane orange, a strategic approach that is aimed at visualizing the self-healing effect of the combination of these different color tones. Figure 6a,b shows the result of this experiment. After a period of 1 h at 37°C with no additional forcing effect, green shades are developed at the intersection of the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel fragments. Conversely, as shown in Figure 6a, OK-GUM-GEL pieces showed insufficient adhesion after 1 h and no mixing of the two pigments.

FIGURE 5: DSC results of (a) OK-GUM-GEL and (b) OK-GUM-GELSA. XRD crystallization characterizations of (c) OK-GUM-GEL, OK-GUM-GELSA (7.5%), and OK-GUM-GELSA (10%). (d) Gelatin and okra gum samples.

The pronounced color differentiation serves as a concrete indicator of the self-healing effect attributed to SA and highlights its potential for application in regenerative materials (Figure 6b).

The electrical self-healing activity of the OK-GUM-GELSA sample was tested using a simple method involving a light bulb and multimeter (Figures 6c, 6d, 6e, 6f, 6g, and

6h). This experimental approach allows observation of the flexibility of the electrical properties of the hydrogel after the self-healing phase. Figure 6c,e shows that an important result clearly emerges after the self-healing phase in the samples with SA. The bulb retains its brightness at a level comparable to the initial state. This sustained conductivity demonstrates the critical role of SA in maintaining the

FIGURE 6: Visualization of self-healing in the hydrogels with colored fragments 1 h after the cut pieces were assembled: (a) OK-GUM-GEL and (b) OK-GUM-GELSA. (c–e) Electrical self-healing test of OK-GUM-GELSA using the light bulb method: (c) OK-GUM-GELSA samples before cutting, (d) cut, and (e) after self-healing. (f–h) Electrical self-healing test of OK-GUM-GEL: (f) OK-GUM-GEL samples before cutting, (g) cut, and (h) after self-healing.

electrical properties of the hydrogel after self-healing thanks to the ionic nature of the interactions in the hydrogel structures. The presence of the SA influences conductivity by creating crystalline complexes and intramolecular crosslinks within the hydrogel polymer chains [64]. Moreover, the resistance of the healed hydrogel returned to 96.2% of its original state in a short time. In contrast, samples without SA showed a noticeable decline in conductivity after self-healing. Consequently, the light bulb emitted a weaker light compared to its initial state (see Figure 6f,h). These results shed light on the practical consequences of integrating SA into hydrogel matrices, not only for their self-healing abilities but also for the preservation of electrical conduc-

tivity. These findings contribute to the expanding spectrum of functional hydrogel materials, providing promising advances in a variety of fields, including biomedical applications and flexible electronics, where flexible and adaptable materials are required.

As the last of the self-healing tests, a tensile test was applied to hydrogel samples. As can be seen from the graph in Figure 7a,b, after the hydrogel pieces were cut and brought together, the mechanical recovery rate was calculated as 95% for the OK-GUM-GELSA sample and 78% for the OK-GUM-GEL sample. The healed state of the produced hydrogel can also be seen in Figure 7c. The recovery rate of the sample with SA added was higher thanks to the

FIGURE 7: (a) Mechanical recovery rate of hydrogels after self-healing. (b) Stress–strain curves of OK-GUM-GELSA samples before and after self-healing. (c) Healing visualization of OK-GUM-GELSA manually. (d) Illustration of self-healing stages of OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel samples.

dual network and physical crosslinking between okra gum-GEL and GEL-SA. The self-healing stages and the chemical bonds formed are visualized in Figure 7d.

3.7. Swelling Ratio. For preparing the buffer solution, a mixture of boric acid (H_3BO_3 , Merck), orthophosphoric acid

(H_3PO_4 , $\geq 99.9\%$, density 1.71 g/cm^3 , melting point 21°C , $\text{pH} < 0.5$), and acetic acid ($\geq 99.9\%$, H_3CCOOH , MW: 60.05 g/mol , boiling point 118°C , melting point 17°C , density 1.05 g/cm^3) was titrated with 0.2 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH , MW: 40 g/mol , boiling point 1390°C , melting point 323°C , density 2.13 g/cm^3) to achieve the desired pH values.

The swelling ratio of the gum obtained from okra stem waste was calculated by adding 1 g of dry okra gum to 25 mL of distilled water in a 25-mL glass Stoppard measuring cylinder and measuring the resulting volume.

Swelling tests of the resulting gum hydrogel were conducted gravimetrically in three stages. First, the dried okra gum hydrogel, which had been dried to a constant weight, was placed in Britton–Robinson buffer (BRB) solution (pH = 7.4) and allowed to swell at 37°C. The swollen hydrogels were periodically removed from the BRB solution, weighed, and then returned to the swelling medium. Swelling ratios (percentage) over time were calculated using Equation (2):

$$\text{Swelling ratio (\%)} = \frac{My - Mk}{Mk} \times 100. \quad (2)$$

In this equation, My and Mk represent the weights of the swollen (wet) and dry okra gum hydrogel strips, respectively. Swelling tests continued until the hydrogels reached a constant weight, known as the equilibrium swelling value, which was determined after 24 h. In the second stage, the effect of temperature on swelling ratios was investigated. Gravimetric measurements were conducted at temperatures ranging from 4°C to 70°C in pH = 7.4 buffer for 24 h. Swelling ratios were determined using Equation (2). In the third stage, the effect of pH on swelling ratios was examined. Swelling values of hydrogels were monitored at pH 2–12 at 37°C for 24 h, and swelling ratios were calculated using Equation (2). All measurements were recorded and repeated three times [45, 65].

The swelling of prepared hydrogels was investigated under maximum water conditions and at different temperatures ranging from 4°C to 70°C over a period of 24 h in pH 7.4 buffer. The results are presented in Figure 8.

The swelling behavior of hydrogels is crucial because they need to maintain appropriate mechanical properties while absorbing water. Hydrogels that can modulate their swelling under specific external conditions are known as smart hydrogels. For OK-GUM-based hydrogels, swelling values increased rapidly within the first 6 h and stabilized after 24 h. Tests conducted for up to 48 h confirmed that the hydrogels reached equilibrium swelling values at 24 h, followed by temperature and pH tests over the same period. The swelling value of the OK-GUM hydrogel was 790%, while the GEL hydrogel exhibited a swelling value of 829%. The swelling rate of the OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel decreased with varying composition (Figure 8a), showing stable swelling after the initial 12 h and consistent behavior thereafter. A reduction in GEL content within the OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel led to decreased swelling. Additionally, incorporating SA in different proportions into the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel reduced its swelling value, suggesting that SA affected water diffusion rates and relaxation behavior within the hydrogel, impacting crystallization [66].

OK-GUM-GEL and OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels exhibited increased molecular mobility with rising ambient temperatures up to room temperature (Figure 8b). Elevated temperatures enhance intermolecular water diffusion, thereby increasing swelling. However, as temperature increased, the molecular mobility of the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel was

compromised by insufficient hydrogen bonding interactions. This resulted in the hydrogel's porous structure being less effective at retaining water, with freely moving water molecule chains filling existing voids, leading to reduced swelling values. This phenomenon was also observed in the OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel. In the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel, higher temperatures adversely affected hydrogen bonding interactions, promoting crystallization (Figure 8c). Additionally, SA chains present in the matrix interacted with existing voids, causing decreased swelling values as these chains, interacting more with water molecules, moved away from the structure with increasing temperature [67].

The changes in pH values of OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels indicate that increasing SA content lowers the pH of the hydrogels. Swelling values tend to be higher in basic environments. GEL contains amino acid structures that achieve equal ionization of carboxylic acid and amino groups at a pH known as the isoelectric point (pI), which ranges from 4.68 to 5.26. Consequently, while the swelling value of GEL hydrogel increases, the pH of OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel at pH 5.2 contributes to decreased swelling values [32, 61].

Increasing the percentage of SA in OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel led to stable increases in swelling rates for up to 6 h. However, swelling rates decreased dramatically after 12 h with the addition of 5% and 7.5% SA, and a similar dramatic decrease was observed with 10% SA. This decline can be attributed to the formation of intermolecular and intramolecular hydrogen bonds by the carboxylic acid groups of SA [68]. Recent interest in SA for hydrogel production is due to its solubility at various pH levels, excellent hydrophilicity, and good biocompatibility. Increased SA content has been associated with decreased swelling ratios, and the reduction in pH levels further supports this dramatic decline in swelling ratios (Figure 8e,f) [69].

3.8. Degradation Behavior. Hydrogel strips made from dried okra stem waste were immersed in BRB solution (pH = 7.4) at 37°C to allow swelling. After 24 h, the hydrogels reached their equilibrium swelling value, and their weight was recorded as the fully swollen weight (Mm). The hydrogels were then removed from the BRB solution, weighed, and returned to the solution. This process was repeated at specified intervals over 30 days, with weights recorded as Mt . Degradation rates were calculated using Equation (3). All measurements were repeated three times for accuracy:

$$\text{Degradation rate (\%)} = \frac{Mm - Mt}{Mm} \times 100. \quad (3)$$

Figure 8d illustrates the degradation behavior of OK-GUM-based hydrogels. Water molecules diffusing into the hydrogels cause the OK-GUM-based layers to expand, creating additional space for freely moving chains within the hydrogel. Over time, these chains may interact with water molecules and migrate outside the hydrogel. However, the presence of SA in OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels limits this distribution within the structure, indicating reduced degradation.

FIGURE 8: (a) Swelling ratios of OK-GUM-based hydrogels. (b) Behavioral changes with temperature. (c) pH changes of OK-GUM-GEL and OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels. (d) Degradation behavior over time. (e) pH changes with varying SA content in OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels. (f) Effect of SA content on swelling behavior in OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogels.

4. Conclusion

In this study, hydrogel production was approached with a waste evaluation and zero-waste strategy, aiming to generate valuable products from sustainable and renewable resources. Polysaccharide-based okra gum powder was extracted from okra stem waste using a digestion bath, with a yield of 27%. To enhance the gelation and physical properties of the hydrogels, a binary polymer combination with GEL was developed. To reinforce the delicate structure and extend the lifespan of the natural hydrogels, SA, a nontoxic, biodegradable, and economical chemical, was used as a natural crosslinker. The resulting hydrogels exhibited a double network structure and self-healing properties due to the synergistic interaction between the crosslinker and the dual polymer matrix.

Characterization of the hydrogel structures was performed using SEM, FTIR, DSC, and XRD. The results of the self-healing tests indicated that SA and GEL-doped hydrogels exhibited high self-healing properties. Mechanical tests revealed a self-healing rate of 95% and a recovery rate in electrical conductivity of 96.2%. These findings underscore the potential of SA and okra gum as crucial components in the development of robust and self-healing hydrogel systems. The OK-GUM hydrogel from okra plant stems maintained stable swelling values beyond 24 h, while the OK-GUM-GEL hydrogel showed balanced swelling. Adding SA to the OK-GUM-GELSA hydrogel decreased swelling values due to insufficient hydrogen bonding, which filled voids with water molecules and caused the chains to move away from the structure at higher temperatures. Degradation values remained stable with SA addition, showing no further degradation.

Our hydrogel system is highly scalable due to the abundance of okra stem waste, the simplicity of the chemicals, and the straightforward processing steps involved. The synthesis relies on water-based extraction, mild heating, and SA crosslinking, eliminating complex modifications or hazardous reagents, making it suitable for large-scale production. Additionally, the incorporation of SA enhances electrical conductivity, enabling applications in strain, pressure, humidity, and touch sensors. These results also highlight the potential of SA as an effective crosslinking agent, improving the self-healing properties of polysaccharide-based hydrogels. Such enhancements make these hydrogels promising for sustainable applications like hydrogel sensors, providing eco-friendly solutions for monitoring physiological and environmental changes. Their enhanced self-healing properties contribute to more durable and reliable sensors for various electronic applications, including Internet of Things (IoT) systems for real-time motion tracking, biosignal monitoring, and smart healthcare applications, further demonstrating their scalability and technological potential.

Data Availability Statement

The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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